

Impactful Public Administration Research

Guidelines for Living Labs, Design Science, and Transdisciplinary Research

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Introduction

Research methods in public administration research have been strengthened over the past decade with much emphasis on experimental research, but there has been a strong focus on rigor rather than relevance. In a series of publications, I have been working on developing guidelines for impactful public administration research on the basis of methods for living labs, design science, and transdisciplinary research. These guidelines can help researchers to strengthen their research design and practices by explicitly considering the various choices in research processes.

These publications explore the value of research methods that are well known in other academic fields but are often less familiar to researchers in public administration. These publications aim to provide insights and guidelines for applying research methods in public administration research that can strengthen societal impact. A key aspect of all these methods is that they entail direct engagement with public administration practices to provide value while also contributing to academic knowledge.

This overview paper provides the references to six articles – one on living labs, four on design science and one on transdisciplinary research – which have been published in various journals in the period 2020 – 2025. The abstracts of all papers are presented and also a link to the full paper. I hope this series of papers helps to increase the impact of public administration research and triggers new academic debates on how to use innovative approaches from other disciplines to strengthen our academic field.

Living lab research

Dekker, R., Franco Contreras, J., & Meijer, A. (2020). [The living lab as a methodology for public administration research: A systematic literature review of its applications in the social sciences](#). *International Journal of Public Administration*, 43(14), 1207-1217.

‘Living labs have become a promising methodology for public administration research to design and study public innovations. Surprisingly, public administration research has paid scant attention to living labs to date. An obvious obstacle to the application of a living lab approach in public administration is unclarities about the value, validity and application of this methodology. This study systematically reviews current applications of living labs in social sciences and links this to opportunities for public administration research. It presents a set of guidelines for the use of living labs in public administration research and reflects upon the value of this specific methodology.’

Dekker, Franco Contreras & Meijer, 2020: 1207

Design science

Romme, A. G. L., & Meijer, A. (2020). [Applying design science in public policy and administration research](#). *Policy & Politics*, 48(1), 149-165.

Ruijter, E., Dingelstad, J., & Meijer, A. (2023). [Studying complex systems through design interventions probing open government data ecosystems in the Netherlands](#). *Public Management Review*, 25(1), 129-149.

Van Hout, M. A., Braams, R. B., Meijer, P., & Meijer, A. J. (2024). [Designing an instrument for scaling public sector innovations](#). *Science and Public Policy*, 51(4), 654-668.

Meijer, A. (2025). [Design science in public administration: producing both situational interventions and generic knowledge](#). *Perspectives on Public Management and Governance*, 8(1), 1-11.

‘There is increasing debate about the role that public policy research can play in identifying solutions to complex policy challenges. Most studies focus on describing and explaining how governance systems operate. However, some scholars argue that because current institutions are often not up to the task, researchers need to rethink this ‘bystander’ approach and engage in experimentation and interventions that can help to change and improve governance systems. This paper contributes to this discourse by developing a design science framework that integrates retrospective research (scientific validation) and prospective research (creative design). It illustrates the merits and challenges of doing this through two case studies in the Netherlands and concludes that a design science framework provides a way of integrating traditional validation-oriented research with intervention-oriented design approaches. We argue that working at the interface between them will create new opportunities for these complementary modes of public policy research to achieve impact.’

Romme & Meijer, 2020: 149

‘Recently, we have seen a rising interest in the study of complex systems in public administration. This paper demonstrates how specific design interventions, also referred to as ‘probes’, can be used to investigate complex systems. The value of this strategy is demonstrated by probing three open data ecosystems in the Netherlands. The probes produce a new understanding of the interrelations between underlying patterns and dynamics of open government data practices. Our research shows that probing is a promising research strategy that can produce rigorous academic knowledge on the underlying patterns and dynamics of complex systems in public administration.’

Ruijter, Dingelstad & Meijer, A. 2023: 129

‘Governments worldwide invest in developing and diffusing innovations to deal with wicked problems. While experiments and pilots flourish, governments struggle to successfully scale innovations. Public sector scaling remains understudied, and scholarly suggestions for scaling trajectories are lacking. Following a design approach, this research develops an academically grounded, practice-oriented scaling instrument for planning and reflecting on the scaling of public sector innovations. We design this instrument based on the academic literature, an empirical analysis of three scaling projects at the Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, and six focus groups with practitioners. This research proposes a context-specific and iterative understanding of scaling processes and contributes a typology of scaling barriers and an additional scaling strategy to the literature. The presented instrument increases our academic understanding of scaling and enables teams of policymakers, in cooperation with stakeholders, to plan and reflect on a context-specific scaling pathway for public sector innovations.’

Van Hout, Braams, Meijer & Meijer, 2024: 564

‘Design science is making a comeback in the discipline of public administration: inspired by the growing popularity of design thinking, various scholars have highlighted the value of design science for the public sector. This theoretical and methodological article aims to contribute to the academic value of design science and focuses on the “double burden” of design science: how can it be applied in such a way that it generates both (relevant) situational interventions and contributes to (robust) generic academic knowledge? We identify which types of generic academic knowledge can be generated through design science in public administration: theoretical knowledge, design exemplars, methodological knowledge, and normative knowledge. We use these four types of generic knowledge to develop a new perspective on design science. We also present guidelines for design research that aim to generate both situational interventions and generic knowledge. These guidelines emphasize the need to be more rigorous and systematic in the process of design research as to ensure the validity and reliability of the contributions to generic knowledge for the discipline of public administration.’

Meijer, 2025: 1

Transdisciplinary research

Meijer, A. J., & Ettliger, K. (2025). [Transdisciplinary public administration research: developing and testing a model for transdisciplinary knowledge integration in the public sector](#). *Perspectives on Public Management and Governance*, 8(2), 106-120.

‘While transdisciplinarity—a combination of interdisciplinary work and coproduction of knowledge with practitioners—has become increasingly popular in various disciplines as a research approach to investigate and tackle wicked problems, its application in public administration research is still limited. Transdisciplinary research contains elements of well-known approaches for impactful research in our field. The notion of transdisciplinarity provides added value by explicitly addressing the combination of interdisciplinary and coproductive knowledge creation and by grounding the approach in the philosophy of science of applied research. This article discusses the value of transdisciplinarity for public administration research and illustrates what it means to do transdisciplinary work in the public sector. More specifically, we develop a conceptual model of transdisciplinary knowledge integration in the public sector with an identification of limiting factors and capacities for overcoming them. We conduct empirical research to test the value of this model: a case of science-government collaboration around datafication in regional and local government in the Netherlands. The empirical test of the conceptual model highlights its value for developing and assessing transdisciplinary research and extends our understanding of the transdisciplinary capacity of public organizations as an essential condition for knowledge integration.’

Meijer & Ettliger, 2025: 106

Conclusions

This series of papers is certainly not an end point for the development of impactful methods for public administration research. The search for better methods needs to continue in order to improve the rigor and relevance of our academic discipline. Labels such as living labs and transdisciplinary research are often used in a rather loose manner and without precisely indicating what these methods mean and how they are applied. I hope these papers contribute to realizing more precision in research papers.

In time, I hope these methods will find their place in methods handbooks and courses at universities, so that researchers and students will learn to apply these impactful methods in their work. Applying these methods is important for realizing impact, and it is also a wonderful opportunity for learning. As the quote generally attributed to psychologist Kurt Lewin goes, if you really want to understand a phenomenon, you have to try to change it. Having worked with all these methods, I certainly agree. And I hope many of you will be stimulated to start experimenting with these impactful research methods.